

PEDAGOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: *The teacher is the elite layer of the society. The main task of this article is to prepare future teachers and analyze their requirements.*

Keywords: *pedagogical skills, social requirements, folk pedagogy, high level of culture, national values, ideological treasure, moral heart, professional activity.*

INTRODUCTION

A teacher is a person with a very high level of culture. He needs to know a lot. Nowadays, he should be aware of the achievements and news in the field of science he is studying. In order to teach students daily activities, he should regularly study, learn, fill and deepen his knowledge. So, the main thing of a pedagogue, pedagogic skill is independent study¹. It is clear to everyone that after the independence of Uzbekistan, there were great changes in the field of education, in terms of restoration of national morals and manners, and in terms of further development of national values. It should not be forgotten that the great future of the state is the young people who have deep knowledge and pure morals. Pedagogical skill is not an innate or hereditary trait, but a product of research and creative work. This multifaceted pedagogical activity is based on creative work. If we look at the professional skills program of the pedagogue in practice, then the first place is its integral quality - skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

¹ Kadirova F.R, Toshpolatova SH.Q, Kayumova N.M., Agzamova M.N. "Preschool Pedagogy" T.: Tafakkur, T- 2019. Textbook.

In the higher education of pedagogy, the process of adaptation to education is carried out with the help of staff serving future teachers, elements of the material base and many other tools. A perfect pedagogical system was created by Jan Amos Comenius. Relying on the advanced ideas of his time, he made a call to "teach everyone to everything". His great treatise "Great Didactics" is considered one of the first works of theoretical pedagogy. J. J. Rousseau (1712-1858), (I. G. Pestolotsy, A. Destervenrg, R. Owen (1771-1858), A. N. Radishchev (1749-1802), V. G. Belinsky, A. Gersen, I. I. Pirogov, N. G. Chernishevsky (1822-1899) , N.D. Dobrolyubov helped a lot. K.D. Ushinsky made a great contribution to the development of the theory of pedagogy. He is called the father of Russian pedagogy. It is considered an indispensable condition for any discipline to stand out and function normally².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pedagogy teaches that the purpose of education changes depending on the requirements of society and the age characteristics of students. Reveals the components of education and the connections between them. On this basis, education summarizes the experiences in the field of education, shows the prospects and ways of the future development of education. Today, in the period of independence, in the spirit of the ideas of independence, the time has come to restore the ancient folk tradition, to use rich and colorful folk pedagogy in education. Genres such as epics, fairy tales, lapar, proverbs, quick sayings, and riddles, which have not lost their essence in modern education, are of great importance in the education of the young generation in the period of independence.

It is also important for a teacher to be able to analyze himself in gaining professional competence. Self-analysis is a study of the essence of the practical actions organized by the pedagogue in professional activity. Through self-analysis, the pedagogue has the opportunity to objectively evaluate himself.

After all, it is important for pedagogues to have the qualities of professional competence that they have the skills of self-evaluation. Self-assessment is a person's assessment of himself through self-analysis. Self-assessment allows the subject to calculate his personal capabilities, give an objective assessment of himself, and ensure self-satisfaction. Self-assessment should help a person to reveal his abilities on his own. Self-

² Akhmedzhanov M.M., Khojaev B.Q., Hasanova Z.D. Pedagogical skills - Bukhara State University, 2014

assessment is difficult, but a person can be directly trained for it. As with any specialist, a number of factors affect the pedagogue's ability to effectively evaluate himself³.

Pedagogical profession is individual in its essence. The vital role of every pedagogue is to be a master of his work, a master is expressed as very advanced, knowledgeable or skillfully performing his work. Pedagogical skills are visible in his work. First of all, a pedagogue should be well versed in the laws and mechanisms of the pedagogical process. In this sense, the general skills of the pedagogue and his pedagogical technique are of great importance. Skill is a special power. It is impossible to become a master at a high or low level. Mastery may or may not be attained. A real master is beautiful only during his work. Achieving pedagogical skills is achieved with certain personal qualities of the pedagogue. Pedagogical skill represents the development of pedagogical activity at a high level, acquisition of pedagogical techniques, as well as the personality of the pedagogue, his experience, civil and professional status.

Pedagogical skill as a category has its own scientific basis. The scientific approaches of recent years have made it possible to draw the following conclusion in relation to this situation: pedagogical skill is understood as a bright manifestation of individuality in professional activity.

The structure of the characteristics of the specialist's socio-perceptive competence:

- accuracy of perception, understanding and assessment of other people;
- the ability to establish a systematic relationship with social entities;
- being able to adequately model the behavior and characteristics of the perceived person;
- to be able to use various criteria in the process of interpersonal evaluation, etc.

In order to form professional competence in future specialists, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of observability, that is, the development of perceptive, cognitive, reflexive, empathic, motivational and prognostic aspects. In order to acquire social-perceptive competence in the process of pedagogical activity and communication, the specialist must have humanitarian, social-reflexive, knowledge and skills, a positive professional "I" image, some personal qualities (intellect, will,

³G.I.KASANOVA "Advantages of using programmed teaching technology in the educational process" Jizzakh: 2020. 420 pages. 223-225

it is advisable to engage in activities related to the formation of empathy, observation, kindness, emotional tolerance, etc.)⁴.

CONCLUSION

Despite the fact that there are so many definitions of pedagogical skill, some aspects of skill are definitely expressed in them. Pedagogy is an honorable but very difficult profession. To be good, it is not enough to master pedagogical theory. Because in the pedagogical theory, the general laws and rules of teaching and upbringing of children, generalized methodological ideas are stated, attention to the individual characteristics of young people is emphasized. Preschool education life is a small pedagogical process and is very diverse. There are situations that do not correspond to the pedagogical theory. This requires extensive knowledge, thorough practical training, high pedagogical skills and creativity from pedagogues.

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